

Chapter 1

THE PROBLEM AND ITS BACKGROUND

1.1 Background of the Study

Archiving all academic papers of GCCCS students, Managing and accessing academic projects like theses and capstone papers is a growing challenge for schools and colleges. Physical storage systems are inefficient, requiring increasing space, and are vulnerable to deterioration over time. With the rising number of submissions each year, locating specific records becomes difficult, making archives harder to manage and less accessible for students, faculty, researchers, and future researchers. Jomarie Del Rosario BSIT 4B, Papasa yan ako pa!!!!!!!!!!!!!! Blessed Me Oh Lord.

Welcome to the new system created or developed by Gordon College CCS Students ETHRIVE: An Electronic Theses and Higher Research Information Vault Exchange A practical research is a must solution for all problems is the ETHRIVE system to these problems is implementing a electronic/digital archiving system. This transition would preserve academic

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work more effectively, eliminate physical storage issues, and provide easier access to valuable research. However, a basic digital archive may not be sufficient. To address the issue fully, a more comprehensive web-based system is needed—one that offers wide accessibility and advanced features.

This study addresses these challenges by creating a platform that is accessible within and outside the institution. This system will enable students, faculty, and external users to search and retrieve research papers, theses, and capstone projects easily. It will also allow faculty to archive their own research, supporting interdisciplinary collaboration. The system will include features for organizing projects by category and track user engagement, such as downloads and views, to provide insights into the use of these documents.

By introducing this e-archiving solution, we aim to create a userfriendly, scalable platform that not only preserves academic work but also fosters knowledge-sharing and improves accessibility for the academic community and beyond.

1.2 Theoretical and Conceptual Framework

This study is grounded in Shannon's Information Theory (1948), which informs the efficient data management needed for the proposed digital archive. Conway (2010) emphasizes digital preservation's role in sustaining academic resources, while Kim and Lee (2020) discuss how digital repositories foster interdisciplinary collaboration, aligning with the study's knowledgesharing goals. Liu and Chen (2022) highlight the impact of digital archives on student learning, underscoring accessibility's importance, and Williams (2019) addresses technical considerations for a robust system, supporting the study's focus on efficiency and reliability. These references collectively validate the study's design and objectives.

1.2.1 Theoretical Framework

Information Theory

This study is anchored in the theoretical support Claude Shannon (1948) established in Information Theory, which focuses on the quantification, storage, and communication of information. It focuses on how information can be efficiently encoded and transported over communication channels with

minimal loss. In the context of this study, Information Theory means that the digital archiving system should efficiently handle data storage and retrieval procedures, allowing users to readily access and share academic works. The concepts of this theory influence the architecture of the system, maximizing data organization and increasing user experience by offering explicit information retrieval pathways. By implementing these concepts, the archiving system can improve the accessibility and use of academic resources, encouraging knowledge sharing among students, educators, and researchers.

Figure 1. Claude E. Shannon Information Theory

- **System Requirements:** Storage space, hardware, and software for digitizing, storing, and accessing documents

Constructivist Learning Theory

The study is not supported by the liberty Constructivist Learning Theory, primarily associated with educational theorists like Piaget (1980) and Vygotsky (1962), posits that learners construct their understanding and knowledge of the world through experiences and reflection. This theory emphasizes the importance of active engagement and collaboration in the learning process.

In the context of this study, Constructivist Learning Theory suggests that a digital archiving system can enhance educational outcomes by providing students and researchers with accessible resources that encourage exploration and critical thinking. By facilitating access to a wide range of academic works, the system allows users to engage with diverse viewpoints and methodologies, thereby fostering a deeper understanding of the subject matter. Furthermore, the theory highlights the value of collaboration, indicating that the system should support interaction among users, such as sharing insights or commenting on works, which can enhance collective learning and knowledge generation.

Figure 2. Constructivist Learning Theory

1.2.2 Conceptual Framework

1. Input

- **Users:** Faculty, students, and researchers of Gordon College
- **Data:** Existing physical thesis and capstone projects, metadata (e.g., author, title, year, program), user login credentials, and search queries

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- **System Requirements:** Storage space, hardware, and software for digitizing, storing, and accessing documents
- **Funding and Resources:** Budget and support from Gordon College for system development and maintenance
- **Existing Challenges:**
 - Space limitations and physical deterioration of documents
 - Difficulty in accessing specific documents
 - Increasing volume of physical submissions

2. Process

- **Digitization:** Converting physical documents to digital files through scanning and cataloging
- **Data Organization:** Metadata tagging for easy search and retrieval (e.g., using categories like year, author, project type)
- **Database Management:** Storing digital files and metadata in a structured, accessible database
- **User Authentication:** Secure login and access control for students, faculty, and researchers

- **Search and Retrieval System:** Implementing a user-friendly search function for locating documents based on keywords, authors, topics, or years
- **Maintenance and Security:** Regular updates, backup, and security protocols to protect data integrity and prevent unauthorized access

3. Output

- **Digital Archive:** A comprehensive, searchable digital archive for thesis and capstone projects
- **Enhanced Accessibility:** Improved access to academic documents, supporting research and learning
- **Preservation of Documents:** Long-term preservation of academic records without the physical space limitations
- **Increased Knowledge Sharing:** Easier dissemination of research findings among students, faculty, and external researchers
- **Institutional Efficiency:** Streamlined document management for Gordon College, reducing reliance on physical storage and enhancing operational efficiency

Figure 2. Digital Archiving and Knowledge Dissemination

1.3 Statement of the Problem

This study aims to examine the challenges and potential solutions related to academic archiving, focusing on the issues of limited physical storage, accessibility constraints, and the benefits of transitioning to a digital archiving system. To address the above problem, the study seeks answers to the following questions:

- 1.** What challenges are associated with physical archiving?
 - 1.1 What issues arise from storage limitations, and how do they impact the preservation of academic works?

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- 1.2 How do current methods of storing physical theses and capstone projects affect the ease and efficiency of record retrieval for students, faculty, and staff?
2. How does an increasing submission volume impact storage and accessibility?
 - 2.1 In what ways does the growing volume of theses and capstone submissions worsen existing challenges in storage and accessibility?
 - 2.2 How do physical storage methods limit the scalability and effectiveness of the archiving process?
3. What limitations does physical storage place on academic accessibility?
 - 3.1 How does physical archiving restrict access to academic research, and what impact does this have on the research and educational needs of students, faculty, and researchers?
 - 3.2 How does limited accessibility prevent academic documents from supporting ongoing research and knowledge-sharing

efforts?

4. What are the potential benefits of a digital archiving system?

4.1 How could a digital archiving system help address current challenges in document preservation and retrieval?

4.2 In what ways could an e-archiving system improve accessibility and encourage knowledge-sharing within the academic community?

1.4 Significance of the Study

CHED Higher Educational Institutions. The study aims to reduce physical storage needs and preserving documents digitally, the system supports long-term accessibility and sustainability, enhancing institutional resource management.

RDCES Research Development Community Extension and Services. The study improves access to academic resources, aiding RDCES staff in efficiently supporting students, faculty, and community research needs. It also promotes interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge-sharing.

Students. The study provides access to past research provides valuable guidance, fostering academic growth and supporting new research efforts.

1.5 Scope and Limitation of the Study

The concept of theses, research, and capstone project archiving revolves around access to and storage of past works. With the increase in technology, several colleges have incorporated the use of electronic archive systems to store research works to provide easy access to such works and improve their digital output. This study focuses on the creation of an EArchiving System for Gordon College to manage, preserve, and offer access to theses, capstone projects, and other higher-level information. These academic documents will be digitally stored, allowing for efficient retrieval, greater organization, and long-term preservation. The system will contain capabilities such as search functionality, user access levels (Administrator, Faculty/Staff, Student, and Researchers/General Users), and digital document management to improve each user's accessibility.

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The study will be limited to archiving theses, research, and capstone projects and will not include other types of academic documents or administrative files. The system will primarily cater to the needs of Gordon College but will also allow scalability for other institutions, with their access limited to viewing documents and providing annotations, comments, or suggestions. Moreover, the study will not cover the digitization process of physical documents, assuming that all documents are already available in a digital format for upload.

1.6 Definition of Terms

Archiving System. A structured system used for storing and managing academic documents like theses, capstone projects, and research papers in digital format, improving organization, accessibility, and long-term preservation.

Digital Preservation. The process of maintaining and safeguarding digital files over time to ensure they remain accessible and undamaged, essential for the longevity of academic documents in a digital archive.

Interdisciplinary Collaboration. A feature enabled by the archiving system that allows faculty and researchers from different academic fields to access and share research, supporting joint research initiatives and knowledge-sharing across disciplines.

Information Theory. A theoretical framework by Claude Shannon used in this study to guide the efficient handling of data within the archiving system. It emphasizes the organization and encoding of information for easy retrieval and minimal data loss during storage and transmission

System Usability. Refers to the design quality of the e-archiving system, focusing on ease of use and intuitive navigation to enhance user experience and satisfaction.

User Engagement. The degree to which users actively interact with the archiving system, including activities such as uploading, searching, and accessing documents. High engagement indicates the system's effectiveness and relevance to its users.

Predictors. Variables hypothesized to influence the outcome or performance of the e-archiving system, such as system usability and content

quality. These predictors help determine the factors critical for the system's success.

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Chapter 2

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

2.1 Research Design

The Mixed Methods of Research were used in this study. This approach combines both qualitative and quantitative techniques to address the complexity of the research problem comprehensively.

The methodology used is well-suited for understanding the

multifaceted challenges and solutions in transitioning from physical to digital archiving systems. This allows the researchers to gather statistical insights and contextual understanding, ensuring a robust and practical solution to the identified issues.

A Mixed Methods Research was used because the study aims to quantitatively assess the challenges and benefits of digital archiving systems while qualitatively exploring the user experience and system usability.

The researchers applied quantitative analysis to examine storage constraints, submission volume, and system performance metrics, and qualitative approaches like interviews or observations to capture user feedback and explore system usability in-depth. This methodology ensures that the developed e-archiving system aligns with the needs of its intended users while addressing technical challenges effectively.

2.2 Locale of the Study

The study will be mainly conducted at Gordon College and other Higher Educational Institutions or School Colleges around the Olongapo City. The focus of the research will be on the academic population within the college,

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specifically targeting third-year and above students, faculty members, and researchers who actively engage in academic research activities such as theses and capstone projects. This group is directly involved in producing, archiving, and utilizing academic resources, making them an ideal population for the study.

Gordon College houses multiple academic units, including the College of Computer Studies (**CCS**), College of Hospitality and Tourism Management (**CHTM**), College of Business and Accountancy (**CBA**), College of Education and Arts Sciences (**CEAS**), and College of Health Sciences (**CAHS**). These colleges offer a wide range of academic programs and cater to a diverse student body. The population for this study will include:

- Approximately **250 third-year** and **fourth-year students** across these colleges, who are actively engaged in academic research and are the primary users of theses and capstone project archives.
- Around **56 faculty members**, who play a significant role as advisers and contributors to research and scholarly work within the institution.

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- Researchers affiliated with Gordon College, who rely on access to academic archives for interdisciplinary collaboration and advanced studies.

By focusing on this specific locale and population, the study ensures relevance and applicability, addressing the unique challenges and needs of Gordon College's academic community. The insights gained will guide the design and implementation of an e-archiving system tailored to this environment, improving accessibility, document preservation, and knowledgesharing among its users.

2.3 Population and Sampling Techniques

Snowball sampling was used in this research where we point our person of interest then they are the one who disseminate the questionnaires for us

2.4 Research Instrument

The primary tool for research instruments in this study is survey (questionnaire), designed to gather information effectively and systematically from the target respondents. The survey (questionnaire) is tailored to align

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with the research objectives and focuses on collecting quantitative and qualitative data. It includes both closed-ended questions (Likert scale) for standardized responses and open-ended questions for in-depth insights. The survey will be administered electronically using Google Forms to ensure accessibility and convenience for respondents.

To ensure the reliability and accuracy of the survey instrument, the survey (questionnaire) underwent content validation by subject matter experts. Faculty members and professionals with expertise in the study's domain reviewed the items for clarity, relevance, and alignment with the research objectives. A pilot test was also conducted with a small group of respondents to assess the clarity of the questions and the functionality of the electronic format. Feedback was gathered and incorporated to refine the questionnaire, ensuring that it effectively captures the intended data and minimizes bias or misinterpretation.

Sections or Components:

The survey questionnaire is structured into the following sections:

1. Demographic Information

Collects basic details about the respondents, such as age, role (e.g., student, faculty), and frequency of system use.

2. System Usability and Functionality:

Includes Likert-scale questions to measure respondents' perceptions of the system's ease of use, efficiency, and overall functionality.

3. User Experience and Satisfaction

Explores respondents' experiences with the system, focusing on their satisfaction, engagement, and any encountered challenges.

4. Readiness Assessment

Evaluates the preparedness and capability of users to adopt and integrate the system into their regular activities. This section includes questions related to their familiarity with similar technologies, access to necessary resources, and willingness to transition to the new system.

5. Feedback and Suggestions

Provides open-ended questions for respondents to share detailed feedback, recommendations for improvement, and any additional comments related to the system.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedure

The data gathering procedure for this study will follow a systematic and comprehensive approach, aligned with the Mixed Methods Research design:

Phase 1: Quantitative Data Collection

1. Survey Design and Distribution

- Create structured questionnaires for students, staff, and researchers.
- Consider aspects such as:
 - Current issues with physical archiving.
 - The perceived benefits of a digital archiving system
 - User expectations and requirements.
- Distribute surveys electronically and in-person throughout Gordon College's academic departments.

2. System Performance Metrics

- Collect quantitative data about:
 - Current physical storage capacity
 - Number of annual thesis and capstone project submissions
 - Time spent searching for and retrieving tangible documents
 - Estimated storage space requirements

Phase 2: Qualitative Data Collection

1. Interviews and Focus Groups

- Conduct semi-structured interviews with:
 - Faculty members from different colleges
 - Researchers
 - Students involved in thesis and capstone projects
- Explore in-depth insights about:
 - Challenges in document management
 - Potential features for the e-archiving system

2. Observational Research

- Observe current document storage and retrieval processes
- Document practical challenges faced by users
- Identify potential improvements for the proposed system

Phase 3: Document Analysis

1. Review of Existing Archives

- Analyze current physical archiving methods
- Assess document organization and accessibility

Phase 4: Prototype Testing

1. Initial System Development

- Create a preliminary version of the e-archiving system
- Implement core features based on research findings

2. User Testing and Feedback

- Invite a representative sample of users to test the prototype
- Gather feedback on:
 - System usability
 - Search functionality

□ Document accessibility

- Use feedback for iterative system improvement

2.6 Statistical Treatment of Data

The gathered data from the survey were processed and analyzed using both descriptive and inferential statistical methods:

1. Descriptive Statistics:

- **Frequency Distribution:** To summarize the responses related to user demographics, archival challenges, and system usability.

2. Inferential Statistics:

- **Correlation Analysis:** To determine relationships between user satisfaction and system features.

3. Qualitative Data Analysis:

- **Thematic Analysis:** Responses from interviews were categorized into themes such as usability challenges, accessibility needs, and technical recommendations, providing context to quantitative findings.

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